

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABEL KURUVILLA JACOB bearing USN6SU20DF001 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHAY V V bearing USN6SU20DF002 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHINAV VINOD bearing USN6SU20DF003 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHISHEK SAM PRAVEEN bearing USN6SU20DF004 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ENJOY P J bearing USN6SU20DF005 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GADHASHREE B bearing USN6SU20DF006 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GODWIN VARUGHESE K bearing USN6SU20DF007 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARIKRISHNAN K bearing USN6SU20DF008 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KIRAN KUMAR K bearing USN6SU20DF009 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LIYO BIJU bearing USN6SU20DF010 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MELWIN POLY bearing USN6SU20DF011 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED MUHAD bearing USN6SU20DF012 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIKHIL JOSEPH K J bearing USN6SU20DF013 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAFUVAN A K bearing USN6SU20DF014 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SELSA ANNA VARGHESE bearing USN6SU20DF015 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SIDHARTH SHYAM bearing USN6SU20DF016 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREEHARI S bearing USN6SU20DF017 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore

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